

The Electrocatalytic Stability Investigation of a Proton Manager MOF for the Oxygen Reduction Reaction in Acidic Media

Samaneh Sohrabi¹ · Masoumeh Ghalkhani² · [Saeed Dehghanpour](#)¹

¹ Department of Chemistry, Alzahra University, Tehran, P.O. Box 1993891176, Iran

² Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Shahid Rajaei Teacher Training University, Lavizan, Tehran, P.O. Box 1678815811, Iran

Abstract

In this paper, regarding outstanding electrocatalytic properties of metal organic frameworks for fuel cell applications, we have synthesised and investigated comprehensively the electrocatalytic stability of PCN-222 (PCN = porous coordination network) for the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) in acidic media. ORR is a main reaction that takes part in the cathodic part of a fuel cell and preparation of a stable and efficient electrocatalyst for this reaction will effectively improve the fuel cell output. The 3D heme-like metal organic framework (MOF) was constructed from Fe(III) porphyrin linkers and Zr₆ clusters. The catalyst stability tests manifested that the PCN-222 is much more stable than the other metal macrocycles. The assembled PCN-222 catalyst possesses ultra stability, high activity and excellent tolerance to the crossover effect of methanol, which could be used as a unique alternative to common ORR catalysts in an acidic direct methanol fuel cell.

Keywords: Stability. Metal organic framework. Fuel cell. Acidic media. Oxygen reduction reaction.

Link: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10904-018-1025-2>